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**Advances in Viroid-Host
 Interactions**

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Abstract

Viroids are small, single-stranded, circular RNAs infecting plants. Composed of only a few hundred nucleotides and being unable to code for proteins, viroids represent the lowest level of complexity for an infectious agent, even below that of the smallest known viruses. Despite the relatively small size, viroids contain RNA structural elements embracing all the information needed to interact with host factors involved in their infectious cycle, thus providing models for studying structure-function relationships of RNA. Viroids are specifically targeted to nuclei (family *Pospiviroidae*) or chloroplasts (family *Avsunviroidae*), where replication based on rolling-circle mechanisms takes place. They move locally and systemically through plasmodesmata and phloem, respectively, and may elicit symptoms in the infected host, with pathogenic pathways linked to RNA silencing and other plant defense responses. In this review, recent advances in the dissection of the complex interplay between viroids and plants are presented, highlighting knowledge gaps and perspectives for future research.

1. INTRODUCTION

Viroids are the simplest known infectious agents. Composed exclusively of a small (246–434 nucleotides), circular, single-stranded RNA molecule, viroids replicate and move systemically in host plants, in which they may induce symptoms. In contrast to viruses, viroids do not code for any protein and are neither encapsidated nor protected by a membranous envelope, thus adopting specific strategies to avoid degradation by cellular RNases. In the absence of protein-coding capacity, the catalytic activity needed for viroid infectivity must be provided by cellular enzymes and/or by the viroid RNA itself, thus making viroids useful models to study RNA structural–functional relationships. In addition, viroids are pathogens affecting several agricultural crops (1). Since their discovery about 50 years ago (2, 3), viroids with different biological, structural, and biochemical features have been identified and classified in two families (**Figure 1**). Members of the family *Pospiviroidae* [representative member potato spindle tuber viroid (PSTVd)] replicate and accumulate in the nucleus and contain a central conserved region (CCR) (4), while those of the family *Avsunviroidae* [representative member avocado sunblotch viroid (ASBVd)] replicate and accumulate in chloroplasts and are endowed with self-cleaving activity mediated by ribozymes (5). Recent reviews have addressed in detail different aspects related to the structure (6), cytopathology (7), pathogenesis (8), and host interactions (9, 10) of these infectious RNAs. Here, we present a general overview of these intracellular molecular parasites at frontiers of life, highlighting recent advances and knowledge gaps, which represent promising topics for future investigations.

2. VIROIDS AND VIROID-LIKE RNAs IN NATURE

Viroids replicate and spread in their plant host in the absence of any other coinfecting agent. This feature can be experimentally tested by bioassays, which are also needed to ascertain whether a viroid, fulfilling Koch's postulates, is the causal agent of a plant disease (11) (**Figure 2**). Although time and cost demanding, bioassays are mandatory to discriminate viroids from other viroid-like RNAs reported in plants that have different biological features. This is the case of viroid-like satellite RNAs, which are functionally dependent on a coinfecting helper virus (12), and retroviroid-like elements, which are not infectious and associated with a DNA counterpart (13).

In the past few years, several circular RNAs with the typical hallmarks of viroids have been identified by high-throughput sequencing (HTS) techniques and powerful bioinformatics tools, although autonomous replication has been ascertained for only some of them (14–19). Not depending on any previous knowledge of the infectious agent and being relatively fast and cost-effective, HTS-based approaches are expected to identify many new viroids and viroid-like RNAs in the future. The same methods also seem appropriate to further investigate whether viroids may infect organisms of other kingdoms of life besides plants. Replication of some viroids has been reported in yeast (20), cyanobacteria (21), and fungi (22) used as experimental hosts, but some of these results have been questioned (23). In nature, at least two viroid-like RNAs have been associated with fungi that infect plants, but their close association with mycoviruses suggested that they are satellite RNAs rather than viroids (24). Another viroid-like RNA that does not infect plants is hepatitis delta virus (HDV), a human pathogen with a genome consisting of an approximately 1,700-nucleotide circular RNA molecule that shares with viroids the presence of ribozymes and the replication mechanism. Although HDV replicates autonomously, its infectivity depends on the helper hepatitis B virus (genus *Hepadnavirus*), which provides the envelope needed for HDV transmission. Moreover, unlike viroids, HDV codes for two protein isoforms involved in viral replication and assembly (reviewed in 25). Remarkably, HTS recently identified HDV-like agents in several animals (26).

a Family *Pospiviroidae*

b Family *Avsunviroidae*

Figure 1

Main structural and biological features of viroids classified in the families *Pospiviroidae* and *Avsunviroidae*. (a) Viroids classified in the family *Pospiviroidae* replicate in the nucleus and adopt a rod-like secondary structure containing conserved motifs with biological and taxonomic relevance: the CCR, the TCR, and the TCH (shaded). Members of each genus contain a specific CCR and the TCH (genera *Hostuviroid* and *Cocadviroid* and members of the genus *Coleviroid* with the smallest genome) or the TCR (genera *Apscaviroid* and *Pospiviroid* and members of the genus *Coleviroid* with the largest genome). The approximate locations of the C, P, V, T_L, and T_R domains with putative functional roles in several members of the family are indicated. Red arrows represent flanking inverted repeats that together with the upper part of the CCR can fold in the metastable hairpin I (bottom left), in which conserved nucleotides in all members of the family *Pospiviroidae* are marked in red. The 3D view of an atomic force micrograph of the plus circular PSTVd RNA (bottom right) shows bumps likely corresponding to internal loops or bulges in the proposed conformation. (b) Viroids classified in the family *Avsunviroidae* replicate in the chloroplast; may adopt rod-like (genus *Avsunviroid*), semibranched (genus *Elaviroid*), or branched (genus *Pelamoviroid*) secondary structures; and contain the sequences conserved in most natural hammerhead structures in plus and minus polarity strands (pink and blue boxes, respectively). The tertiary interaction between two loops identified in members of the genus *Pelamoviroid* is indicated with dashed lines. The hammerhead ribozyme structure (bottom left), characterized by tertiary interactions between nucleotides of loops 1 and 2 (gray background), is adopted only during replication and determines the self-cleavage of the viroid RNA at a specific site (arrow). Continuous and dashed lines represent Watson-Crick and noncanonical base pairs, respectively. The 3D view of an atomic force micrograph of the plus linear PLMVd RNA shows a profile consistent with the proposed branched conformation (bottom right). Abbreviations: C, central; CCR, central conserved region; P, pathogenic; PLMVd, peach latent mosaic viroid; PSTVd, potato spindle tuber viroid; TCH, terminal conserved hairpin; TCR, terminal conserved region; T_L, terminal left; T_R, terminal right; V, variable. Both 3D images reproduced from Reference 32 with permission of Taylor & Francis Ltd.

Figure 2

Confirmation of viroid autonomous replication and fulfillment of Koch's postulates. The viroid nature of a small circular RNA is dependent on its ability to systemically infect a plant in the absence of any helper virus (autonomous replication) and needs to be assessed by bioassays. (*Left to right*) The inoculum generally consists of viroid circular forms purified from infected tissues by polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (*upper left*) or dimeric head-to-tail linear RNAs generated ex novo either in vitro by transcription or in vivo by agrobacterium-mediated expression (*bottom left*). After inoculation or agroinoculation of virus-free plants, detection of the viroid RNA in the systemic parts of the inoculated plant [for instance, by Northern blot hybridization as reported in the figure where the circular (C) and the linear (L) forms of the viroid in several samples are detected with a specific molecular probe] will confirm its infectivity in the absence of other coinfecting agents. The reproduction in the inoculated plants of the symptoms observed in the source host will fulfill Koch's postulates, demonstrating that the viroid is the causal agent of a disease.

3. SECONDARY STRUCTURES, 3D MOTIFS, AND METASTABLE CONFORMATIONS OF VIROIDS

Although viroids do not code for any protein, they contain the necessary information for a successful infection, mostly provided by structural elements that may interact with and redirect host factors toward viroid replication and trafficking in the plant. Therefore, viroid RNA structural elements are useful systems to study basic principles of RNA biology and may reveal functional motifs possibly contained in host RNAs (27).

Due to highly self-complementary sequences, the predicted most stable secondary structure of viroid genomic RNAs consists of double-stranded stretches of nucleotides flanked by loops and bulges that may adopt rod-like or multibranched conformations (**Figure 1**). Based on electron microscopy, in silico predictions, and biophysical methods, the rod-like conformation was proposed early on for the representative nuclear-replicating viroid PSTVd and later for the other nuclear viroids (reviewed in 6). They share several motifs, such as the CCR, the terminal

conserved hairpin, and the terminal conserved region (**Figure 1**); based on pairwise comparisons, several adjacent domains with putative functional roles were identified in their rod-like secondary structure (28) (**Figure 1**). The rod-like conformation adopted by the representative member of chloroplast-replicating viroid ASBVd (29) supported the early notion that such a secondary structure was a critical distinguishing feature of all viroids. This belief was dismissed when peach latent mosaic viroid (PLMVd) (30) and other members of the family *Avsunviroidae* were shown to fold into branched or semibranching secondary structures of minimal free energy (**Figure 1**).

The predicted secondary structure of most viroids was confirmed *in vitro*, with some deviations, by selective 2'-hydroxyl acylation analyzed by primer extension (SHAPE) coupled with computer-based prediction of the structure, a technique that interrogates the RNA backbone at single-nucleotide level (reviewed in 10). In PLMVd, the existence of a tertiary structure element composed of two interacting loops (kissing-loop) (**Figure 1**) was also shown by this technique (31). More recently, the native conformation of representative members of nuclear- (PSTVd) and chloroplast-replicating viroids [PLMVd and eggplant latent viroid (ELVd)] was visualized by atomic force microscopy (32) (**Figure 1**). In the case of PLMVd, the presence of Mg²⁺ resulted in the conformation compaction in the wild type but not in a PLMVd mutant in which the kissing-loop was disrupted, thus providing direct physical evidence of the stabilizing role of this tertiary structural element (32).

The relevance *in vivo* of the viroid conformations predicted *in silico* and *in vitro* is supported by the conserved rod-like shape of members of the family *Pospiviroidae* despite their nucleotide sequence diversity (28) and by the similar branched secondary structure, stabilized by a comparable kissing-loop structure, adopted by the chloroplast-replicating viroids PLMVd, chrysanthemum chlorotic mottle viroid (CChMVd), and apple hammerhead viroid, which do not share any sequence identity with each other. Interestingly, in the case of CChMVd, the kissing-loop plays a major role in infectivity (33). Additional evidence of the biological role of viroid conformation derives from studies on the sequence heterogeneity of viroid populations. Due to the low fidelity of the RNA polymerases involved in replication (see Section 4) and the selection pressure imposed by host and environmental constraints, viroids accumulate in the infected tissues as populations of variants with slightly different nucleotide sequences, thus displaying the typical features of quasispecies (reviewed in 34). This sequence variability generally does not affect the proposed conformations, thus supporting strong *in vivo* selection for its preservation. Recently, *in vivo* SHAPE applied to PSTVd and ASBVd showed that in the cells these two viroids mainly adopt conformations almost identical to those predicted by *in vitro* SHAPE (35, 36). More importantly, these studies provided solid evidence that viroids accumulate *in vivo* as free nucleic acids and supported the view that their stability does not rely on interactions with protecting host proteins but most likely depends on intrinsic structural features in viroid RNA. In this context, the circularity and compact conformation, together with the compartmentalization in the nucleus (PSTVd) or in the chloroplast (ASBVd), may strongly enhance viroid resistance to cellular RNases (37, 38).

The spatial conformation of viroid RNAs is expected to be extremely relevant for their biology. A tertiary structural element consisting of non-Watson-Crick base-paired nucleotides resembling the loop E previously reported in archaeal and eucaryal ribosomal RNAs (rRNAs) was identified in the CCR of PSTVd (reviewed in 6) (**Figure 3**). *In vitro* and *in vivo* functional assays revealed that the loop E integrity is essential for PSTVd replication (39). Studies with the closely related citrus exocortis viroid (CEVd) supported the involvement of this structural element in the ligation of linear viroid RNAs into circular forms during replication (see Section 4) (40), with a similar role proposed for the loop E conserved in all viroids of the genus *Pospiviroid*. Phylogenetic analysis and 3D modeling identified alternative structural elements, resembling loop E, in the CCR of other nuclear-replicating viroids that appeared to lack this structural element (41).

Figure 3

Structural motifs of PSTVd involved in replication (*a*) and trafficking (*b*). (*a*) The predicted secondary structure of PSTVd is shown with boxes around the nucleotides forming the CCR (*dashed green lines*). The structural motifs loop E (39) within the CCR and loop 27 (46), which contain non-Watson-Crick base-paired nucleotides critical for replication, are shadowed in orange. The nucleotides forming loops and bulges reported as relevant for replication are indicated in green (42). The G/U pairs important for efficient viroid replication (48) are marked by empty orange boxes. The U/G pair at position 7:353, essential for replication (48), and most of the loops involved in replication lie within the proposed binding region of RNApol II (*boxed, dashed blue line*) (74). The proposed binding site of TFIIIA-7ZF (73) is also indicated (*empty red box, dashed line*). (*b*) The nucleotides forming loops involved in movement (42) are indicated in red. The 3D structural motifs required for PSTVd transit from bundle sheath cells into phloem (loop 7) (43), from palisade mesophyll to spongy mesophyll cells (loop 6 and loop 19) (44, 45), and from epidermis to palisade mesophyll cells (loop 27) (46) are shadowed in blue. The G/U pairs important for systemic trafficking (48) are indicated with empty blue boxes. The two G/U pairs identified as required for entry into phloem (48) are indicated. Coupled G/U pairs required for replication (*a*) or trafficking (*b*) are connected by a line. It is noteworthy that loop 27 and several G/U pairs are involved in both trafficking and replication. Abbreviations: CCR, central conserved region; PSTVd, potato spindle tuber viroid; RNApol II, RNA polymerase II; TFIIIA-7ZF, transcription factor IIIA with seven zinc fingers.

Mutational studies followed by bioassays in planta and in protoplasts identified other loops and bulges in the most stable secondary structure of PSTVd with potential functional roles in its replication and/or trafficking (42) (**Figure 3**). Some of these loops were shown to be highly structured 3D motifs, the disruption of which impaired viroid movement and/or replication (43–46). Interestingly, the progeny of a variant mutated in one of the loops involved in PSTVd trafficking (loop 19, **Figure 3**) recovered movement competence when an alternative 3D motif replaced the mutation (45), thus revealing that functionally relevant tertiary structural elements may emerge de novo and likely act as critical constraints in viroid evolution (47). Recently, an exhaustive mutational analysis of each G/U pair in the proposed PSTVd rod-like structure showed that some of them have functional role(s) in the viroid replication and/or trafficking (48), likely due to the higher conformational flexibility of the G/U wobble pair as compared with canonical Watson-Crick base pairs (49).

The structural elements reported above have been identified in the mature viroid RNAs. However, during the infection cycle, viroids may temporarily adopt alternative (metastable) conformations containing transient structural elements with major biological roles. The prominent metastable conformation for nuclear-replicating viroids is the hairpin I (HPI) formed by the upper CCR strand and two flanking inverted repeats (50) (**Figure 1**). Preservation of HPI in all members of the family *Pospiviroidae*, notwithstanding the sequence divergence in the CCR, is consistent with the relevant function assigned to this structure in viroid replication (see Section 4). Alternative structures not present in the most stable conformation of mature viroids are also the catalytic domains [hammerhead ribozymes (HRzs)] in both polarity strands of chloroplast-replicating viroids. HRzs determine viroid RNA self-cleavage during replication (see Section 4) and have been evolutionarily selected to fold into their active conformation only during viroid RNA transcription (51). HRz active structure consists of a highly conserved core of nucleotides surrounded by three helices, two of which are closed by loops (52) (**Figure 1**). Noncanonical interactions between these two loops stabilize the active conformation of the natural hammerheads and are critical for the ribozyme activity and viroid infectivity (53, 54). Interestingly, the presence of catalytic activities within the small, circular genome of several viroids and viroid-like satellite RNAs supported the proposal by Diener (55) that they could be relics of the RNA world preceding cellular life based on DNA and proteins (56).

Taking into consideration that functional roles of several cellular RNAs rely on modified nucleotides (57), their presence in viroid RNAs should not be excluded. Early studies based on RNase fingerprint analyses of bisulfite-treated RNA preparations did not identify C5-methylcytosine in PSTVd (58). These results were recently confirmed at a single-nucleotide resolution level by RNA bisulfite sequencing and extended to both polarity strands of PSTVd and ASBVd (59). However, many other different modifications have been reported in RNAs (60), and whether one or more of them are transiently or stably present in viroid RNAs is not known.

4. VIROID REPLICATION

Viroids replicate via a rolling circle mechanism based solely on RNA intermediates. Two models, asymmetric (61) and symmetric (62), have been proposed for the members of the families *Pospiviroidae* and *Avsunviroidae*, respectively. The circular RNA of plus polarity (assigned by convention as the most abundant strand in the infected tissues) is reiteratively transcribed in oligomeric RNAs of minus polarity that, in the asymmetric pathway, serve as templates for the synthesis of complementary oligomers (**Figure 4**). In the symmetric model, the minus oligomeric RNAs are cleaved into monomers that, when ligated into circular forms, become the template for the transcription

Figure 4

Replication, movement, and proposed pathogenetic mechanisms of viroids. Viroids move from cell to cell through PD and systemically via phloem, most likely interacting with specific host factors. After entry in the cell, viroids move to the nucleus (family *Pospiviroidae*) or to the chloroplast (family *Asunviroidae*), where they replicate through an asymmetric and symmetric rolling circle mechanism, respectively. Red arrows indicate viroid trafficking pathways. Host proteins and Rzs involved in the viroid replication cycles (black arrows) are indicated. Viroids are triggers and targets of the RNA silencing mechanism (gray arrows). vd-sRNAs, generated by the slicing activity of DCL proteins, are loaded into AGO proteins that may target for degradation the viroid RNAs. RDRs may transform some viroid RNA fragments into additional DCL substrates. vd-sRNAs may guide AGO1 to cognate host mRNAs for their cleavage and degradation, thus impairing the expression of certain host genes and eliciting symptoms. Alternative proposed pathways of pathogenesis (blue arrows) are PTI and ETI activation, interference with translation, and induction of epigenetic changes in the host DNA. Abbreviations: AGO, Argonaute; CsPP2, cucumber phloem protein 2; DCL, Dicer-like; ETI, effector-triggered immunity; MAPK, mitogen-activated protein kinase; mRNA, messenger RNA; NEP, nuclear-encoded RNA polymerase; PAMP, pathogen-associated molecular pattern; PD, plasmodesmata; PTI, pathogen-associated molecular pattern-triggered immunity; RDR, RNA-dependent RNA polymerase; RNAPol II, RNA polymerase II; ROS, reactive oxygen species; rRNA, ribosomal RNA; Rz, ribozyme; tRNA, transfer RNA; vd-sRNA, viroid-derived small RNA.

of oligomers of plus polarity. In both models, the oligomers of plus polarity are cleaved and circularized to generate the mature circular RNA of plus polarity (reviewed in 63) (**Figure 4**).

The study of the enzymatic activities involved in viroid replication yielded surprising results, starting from the enzymes involved in their transcription, which are the DNA-dependent RNA polymerase II (RNAPol II) for the nuclear viroids (64, 65) and the chloroplastic nuclear-encoded RNA polymerase (NEP) for the chloroplast-replicating viroids (66, 67). Interestingly, RNAPol II is also the polymerase implicated in the replication of HDV RNA (reviewed in 68). Both RNAPol II and NEP, known to transcribe host messenger RNAs (mRNAs) from DNA, are forced by viroids to use RNA templates. This template switch could at least partially explain the high mutation rate observed in viroids (69, 70), which in the case of CChMVd was estimated to be the highest among any biological entity (69). Moreover, the use of RNA instead of DNA as template could be indirect evidence of still unknown physiological role(s) of these polymerases in plants. Interestingly, DNA-dependent RNA polymerases of some mammals and bacteria may use RNA templates to transcribe short regulatory cellular RNAs (71, 72).

How viroids and HDV may force host DNA-dependent enzymes to accept RNA templates is not known, but host proteins are likely required. While several transcription factors involved in the RNAPol II-mediated activity on HDV have been identified (68), limited information is available for viroids. Transcription factor IIIA with seven zinc fingers (TFIIIA-7ZF), a spliced variant of the transcription factor TFIIIA-9ZF, has been proposed to be an enhancing auxiliary factor of PSTVd transcription (73). TFIIIA-7ZF binds to the left terminal region of PSTVd (73), where the binding site of RNAPol II (74), the transcription initiation site of PSTVd minus strands (75), and a G/U pair essential for replication (48) also map (**Figure 3**). Because the alternative splicing generating TFIIIA-7ZF is negatively regulated by the ribosomal protein L5 (RPL5), the interaction *in vitro* (76) and *in vivo* (77) of RPL5 with the CCR of PSTVd has been proposed to favor the expression of TFIIIA-7ZF, thus promoting viroid replication. Consistent with this model are the data indicating that transcription of the PSTVd minus polarity strand uses circular PSTVd RNAs as templates, initiating at a specific site (75, 78). Presumably, a specific yet unknown initiation site also exists for the transcription of the plus polarity strand of nuclear-replicating viroids.

The initiation site of NEP-mediated transcription of most chloroplast-replicating viroids has been identified in both polarity strands. It consists of AU-rich terminal loops in ASBVd and short double-stranded RNA (dsRNA) stems including the hammerhead self-cleavage sites in PLMVd (reviewed in 63). In contrast, the initiation sites of the two ELVd polarity strands were mapped at different sequence/structural motifs (79). Information on host factors involved in the transcription of chloroplast-replicating viroids is scant.

The cleavage site of plus RNA oligomers of representative members of the family *Pospiviroidae* [CEVd, hop stunt viroid (HSVd), and apple scar skin viroid] was mapped at equivalent positions in their respective HPI (40) (**Figure 1**). Although the processing enzyme has not been identified, the involvement of a class III RNase has been suggested. In the proposed model, the HPis of two consecutive monomers may interact with each other, generating a transient dsRNA domain appropriate for an RNase III-like mediated cleavage. Importantly, CEVd RNAs processed *in vivo* contained 5'-phosphomonoester and 3'-hydroxyl termini compatible with cleavages mediated by this type of RNases (80).

In contrast to nuclear-replicating viroids, the cleavage of multimeric RNAs of both polarity strands of the chloroplast-replicating viroids is an autocatalytic process mediated by *cis*-acting HRzs (62, 81). Although the activity of the ribozymes is protein independent, host factors could be involved in facilitating the adoption of hammerhead active conformation *in vivo*, as proposed for the PARBP33, a chloroplast protein that binds ASBVd *in vivo* and stimulates the viroid self-cleavage *in vitro* (82).

After cleavage, the replication cycle is completed by circularization of the monomeric RNAs through a ligase catalytic activity. *In vitro* and *in vivo* studies support the involvement of the chloroplastic isoform of the transfer RNA (tRNA) ligase in the circularization of chloroplast-replicating viroids (83). The substrates of this enzyme are 5'-hydroxyl and 2',3'-phosphodiester termini, corresponding to those resulting from the hammerhead-mediated self-cleavage of the oligomeric viroid RNAs. Interestingly, a recombinant form of the eggplant tRNA ligase was able to circularize *in vitro* linear forms of ELVd with the appropriate termini only when they were opened at the cleavage site, suggesting the contribution of specific viroid structural motifs in the ligation process (83). In line with these findings, based on mutational analysis in the nonhost *Escherichia coli* expressing a chloroplastic tRNA ligase, HRz domains of ELVd were suggested to be involved in the *in vivo* circularization of this viroid (84). Surprisingly, it was shown that the enzyme involved in the ligation of PSTVd monomers, and probably of all the other nuclear-replicating viroids, is the nuclear DNA ligase 1 (85), providing an additional example of a host enzyme forced by viroids to replace the canonical DNA substrate with RNA.

Additional efforts are needed to completely dissect viroid replication, including the identification of the enzyme involved in the processing of nuclear-replicating viroids as well as the host factors likely interacting with some of the RNA structural motifs shown to be critical for viroid replication (39, 42, 46, 48) (**Figure 3**; see Section 3).

5. VIROID INTRACELLULAR AND EXTRACELLULAR MOVEMENT

Viroids provided the first evidence that naked, noncoding RNAs can move not only within the cell but also from cell to cell and systemically in their host, thus representing a model for studying RNA transport pathways in plants (86). Once a viroid enters the cell, it has to reach the specific organelle (nucleus or chloroplast) in which replication takes place (**Figure 4**). Early studies in tobacco protoplasts using fluorescent PSTVd transcripts showed that nuclear import is a cytoskeleton-independent process mediated by a saturable receptor likely interacting with viroid sequence or structural motifs (87). Recently, microinjection of PSTVd in the abaxial leaf epidermal cells of *Nicotiana benthamiana* revealed that the efficiency of the nuclear import did not necessarily correlate with the level of viroids in the cytoplasm, strongly suggesting that the nuclear import of viroids is not simply a concentration-dependent process (88). Potential nuclear targeting signals were mapped in the upper strand of the PSTVd CCR (89). Whether a similar signal also exists in viroids with the same or a different CCR has not been investigated. Although the interacting host factor(s) allowing viroid nuclear trafficking have not been conclusively identified, involvement of Virp1—a bromodomain-containing protein binding PSTVd *in vivo* and *in vitro*, endowed with a nuclear localization signal (90) and essential for viroid replication (91)—has been proposed. In support of such a role, the same protein mediates nuclear import of a noncoding satellite RNA (92).

The uneven spatial distribution of the plus and minus polarity strands of PSTVd within the nucleus, with only the plus strand accumulating in the nucleolus (93), suggested the existence of a subnuclear trafficking pathway, likely involving viroid signals and not-yet-identified host protein(s). It has been proposed that RPL5, which binds PSTVd (see Section 4) and accumulates in the nucleolus (94), is part of this pathway (76).

Although the underlying mechanisms are still completely unknown, the ability of chloroplast-replicating viroids to cross the bilayer plastid membrane, which has not been reported for other RNAs, raises the question of whether host RNAs would also enter or exit the chloroplasts through the same pathway(s) used by viroids. Remarkably, foreign mRNAs fused to ELVd or CChMVd RNA are able to enter into chloroplasts (95, 96), indicating that these viroids contain specific chloroplast localization signals.

After exiting the organelles, viroids move to neighboring cells through plasmodesmata (97) and to distal parts of the plant via the phloem (98, 99) (**Figure 4**). Investigation of mechanisms involved in viroid movement mainly focused on PSTVd and revealed a complex trafficking pathway in which structural signals in the viroid RNA, including a bipartite motif (100), highly structured loops (42–46), and G/U pairs at specific positions (48), are needed to cross different cell boundaries in a directional way (**Figure 3**). These findings imply that different interacting host factors are likely involved. The cucumber phloem protein 2 (CsPP2), one of the most abundant proteins in the cucumber phloem, interacts with HSVd *in vitro* and *in vivo*, probably through a dsRNA binding domain (101–103). Interspecies grafting experiments revealed that the ribonucleoprotein complex of HSVd/CsPP2 is translocated from the rootstock to the scion, suggesting the involvement of CsPP2 in the systemic movement of HSVd and probably of cellular RNAs (102). Finally, Solovyev et al. (104) reported evidence for a possible role of 4/1 protein in the long-distance vascular movement of PSTVd.

6. RNA SILENCING AND OTHER DEGRADATION PATHWAYS

While molecular events involved in viroid replication have been studied in depth, information on degradation pathways targeting viroid RNAs is mainly limited to the involvement of RNA silencing, a regulatory mechanism of gene expression and genome integrity maintenance in eukaryotes, which is also implicated in antiviral defense in plants (105). RNA silencing is activated by dsRNAs or highly structured RNAs that are processed by Dicer-like (DCL) endonucleases into small interfering RNAs (siRNAs) or microRNAs (miRNAs). At least four DCLs have been identified in plants—DCL1/DCL4, DCL2, and DCL3—generating small RNAs (sRNAs) of 21, 22, and 24 nucleotides, respectively, with different or partially overlapping functional roles (106). Incorporated into Argonaute (AGO) protein complexes, miRNAs and siRNAs of 21 and 22 nucleotides guide the proteins toward sequence-specific cleavage or inhibition of translation of cognate RNAs, whereas 24-nucleotide siRNAs target cognate DNA to direct RNA-dependent DNA methylation (RdDM) (107).

The identification in infected tissues of different-sized viroid-derived small RNAs (vd-sRNAs) of both polarities, resembling siRNAs, showed that both nuclear- and chloroplast-replicating viroids are targeted by different DCLs for degradation (reviewed in 108). By using transgenic *N. benthamiana* lines with impaired expression of DCLs (singly or in combination), DCL2 and DCL3 were identified as the most relevant in the defense against PSTVd, while DCL4 was proposed to hierarchically act to suppress the effects of DCL2/DCL3 on viroid infectivity (109). An antiviral defense role of DCLs is also supported by the increased accumulation of PSTVd in DCL2/DCL4-knockdown transgenic tomato plants (110). Interestingly, vd-sRNAs of 24 nucleotides were identified only in tissues infected by nuclear-replicating viroids, indicating that chloroplast-replicating viroids likely escape targeting by DCL3 (111, 112). Evidence supporting targeting of viroids by the AGO proteins included immunoprecipitation assays of endogenous AGO1 and of different *Arabidopsis thaliana* AGOs transiently expressed in *N. benthamiana* infected with PSTVd. These experiments revealed that PSTVd-derived sRNAs are loaded into AGO1, AGO2, AGO4, and AGO5. Moreover, transient expression of these four AGOs in *N. benthamiana* leaves reduced PSTVd accumulation, suggesting that, similar to DCLs, AGOs also target viroids for degradation (113). The amplification step of RNA silencing mediated by RNA-dependent RNA polymerases (RdRp) is also part of the plant antiviral defense, as shown by the overaccumulation of PSTVd and the invasion of shoot apical meristems (SAMs) in *N. benthamiana* transgenic lines in which the expression of an RdRp (RDR6) was silenced (112). Partial invasion of the SAM by PSTVd was also observed in RDR6-silenced tomato plants, although it was accompanied by a lower viroid accumulation,

likely caused by the overexpression of RDR1, an RdRp dysfunctional in *N. benthamiana* (114). The antiviral role of RNA silencing is also supported by the resistance or infection retardation induced by viroid dsRNA sequences transgenically delivered or coinoculated in the host plant (reviewed in 115), as well as by the overaccumulation of citrus dwarfing viroid, a nuclear-replicating viroid, in a transgenic citrus plant expressing a viral RNA silencing suppressor (116).

Besides RNases involved in RNA silencing, other RNases could also contribute to the viroid RNA turnover, such as those proposed to generate PSTVd subgenomic RNAs (sgRNAs) of both polarities in three different *Solanaceae* plant hosts (tomato, eggplant, and *N. benthamiana*) (117). PSTVd-sgRNAs had a nuclear localization and did not result from a premature transcription termination. Moreover, their 5'-hydroxyl and 3'-phosphomonoester termini were not compatible with DCL- or AGO-mediated cleavages (which produce 5'-phosphomonoester and 3'-hydroxyl termini). Therefore, it was proposed that these RNAs are generated in the nucleus by one or more still-unidentified endoribonucleases targeting the replicative intermediates (117). Considering that nuclear viroids are replicated by RNAPol II and that mRNA transcription is associated with a quality control mechanism in which RNases are also involved (118), the possibility exists that one or more of these enzymes cotranscriptionally generate PSTVd sgRNAs during viroid replication. Other degradation mechanisms targeting viroids are associated with the activation of nucleases in immature pollen (119). Further characterization of viroid RNA degradation products and the identification of the specific endonucleases acting in the viroid RNA decay pathways are expected to disclose the molecular mechanism regulating viroid RNA turnover.

7. VIROID-INDUCED ALTERATION OF GENE EXPRESSION AND PATHOGENESIS

Viroids can induce different symptoms in infected plants, including stunting; chlorosis; leaf curling; wood and bark alterations; size reduction; and deformation of fruits, tubers, and flowers (120). Initial hypotheses on viroid pathogenesis included direct interactions of the genomic viroid RNA with host factors (10). When vd-sRNAs were discovered, they were proposed to act as miRNAs and direct the sequence-specific cleavage of complementary host mRNA(s) coding for protein(s) crucial for plant development or homeostasis, thus eliciting symptoms (121, 122). The role of this pathway has been documented in the case of two diseases caused by two variants of the chloroplastic viroid PLMVd in peach trees. PLMVd-PC and PLMVd-PYM variants induce a severe albinism [peach calico (PC)] (123) and a peach yellow mosaic (PYM) (124), respectively, and the elicitation of these different symptoms has been strictly associated with a structural domain (pathogenic determinant) differing in sequence and position in the two viroid variants. In both cases, it was shown that specific vd-sRNA(s) derived from the respective pathogenic determinant mediated the cleavage of a cognate host mRNA via an RNA silencing mechanism (**Figure 4**). The mRNAs targeted by the two viroid variants were different, but both encoded proteins involved in the chloroplast biogenesis: the chloroplastic HSP90 (cHSP90) in PC (125) and the thylakoid translocase subunit cpSecA in PYM (124). In both cases, the pathogenic vd-sRNA had a 5'-terminal U compatible with its recruitment by AGO1, which preferentially incorporates miRNAs with the same 5'-terminal nucleotide and targets host mRNAs for degradation. Importantly, phenotypic and chloroplast alterations resembling those observed in PC and PYM diseased peach trees were observed in *Arabidopsis* and/or tobacco in which *cHSP90* and *cpSecA* homologous genes were mutated or silenced, respectively. Therefore, in these pathogenic systems, an initial event, consisting of the silencing of a specific host mRNA directed by a vd-sRNA, was linked by a relatively short signaling cascade with the final macroscopic phenotype (albinism or chlorosis) through the alteration of chloroplast biogenesis (reviewed in 8).

vd-sRNA-mediated degradation of host mRNAs was also shown in tomato plants infected by PSTVd and other nuclear-replicating viroids. The identified targets include mRNAs coding for proteins with several functional roles, i.e., a WD-40 repeat protein, two callose-like synthases (Cal-S11 and Cal-S12), a chloride channel protein CLC-b-like, the ribosomal protein S3a, a protein involved in flowering (FRIGIDA-like protein 3) and proteins involved in plant defense and development (reviewed in 10). In some of these studies, a relationship was reported between the vd-sRNA-mediated silencing of a specific mRNA and the typical viroid-induced symptoms of stunting and leaf curling in tomato. Therefore, the same symptoms appear to be associated with the downregulation of several different tomato genes. In potato, tuber deformation, stunting, and leaf curling symptoms caused by PSTVd were associated with the PSTVd-sRNA-mediated cleavage of the mRNA coding for the transcription factor TCP23, which is involved in plant development and hormonal regulation (126). For HSVd, two possible mRNA targets coding for ethylene-responsive and trihelix transcription factors have been identified in cucumber, although their involvement in HSVd pathogenicity was not demonstrated (127). Therefore, in the case of the members of family *Pospiviroidae*, the scenario involving vd-sRNAs in pathogenesis appears more complex than in chloroplast viroids, possibly because the systemic symptoms frequently taken into consideration (stunting and leaf curling) are complex developmental disorders, likely derived from the contribution of different pathways.

In agreement with this view and regardless of the initial event, alternative pathogenic mechanisms were proposed for nuclear-replicating viroids (**Figure 4**). Transcriptomics studies performed in several viroid-host combinations showed that genes involved in defense, plant hormone signaling, photosynthesis, RNA processing and binding, protein metabolism and modification, and/or RNA silencing were differentially regulated upon viroid infection (reviewed in 128; 129–134). Moreover, several genes involved in plant innate immune responses—such as mitogen-activated protein kinase, pathogenesis-related proteins, resistance proteins, defense-related transcription factors, and genes involved in cell wall biogenesis and reactive oxygen species metabolism—were shown to be induced upon infection by nuclear-replicating viroids, suggesting that viroids can activate pathogen-associated molecular pattern (PAMP)-triggered immunity (PTI) and effector-triggered immunity (ETI) (129–133). In these defense mechanisms, PAMPs are recognized by membrane-associated receptor-like protein kinases to trigger the PTI and ETI defense responses (135). However, how a noncoding viroid may act as a PAMP or as an effector of immunity remains unclear. The ability of viral dsRNA to act as a PAMP and induce PTI has been proposed in *Arabidopsis* (136), opening the possibility that viroid-derived dsRNAs or the quasi-dsRNA viroid structure could trigger these pathways. Interestingly, several protein kinases activated or induced by PSTVd or by related viroids have been reported (137–139), but the role in plant defense responses remains elusive. A global alteration in alternative splicing of host protein-coding genes and in the *trans*-acting function of phased secondary siRNAs has been recently reported in PSTVd-infected tissues, extending the mechanisms by which viroids may affect host gene expression patterns (129). Data on global gene expression modulated by chloroplast-replicating viroids are limited to a single study in fruits of peach trees infected by PLMVd that identified only a low number of genes with statistically significant expression changes (140).

Viroids could also interfere with host translational machinery, thus contributing to the symptomatology. Indirect evidence for this mechanism includes the altered expression of ribosomal genes and translation factors observed in viroid-infected plants (141, 142). Early *in silico* studies suggested that several nuclear-replicating viroids could interfere with preribosomal RNA processing by binding complementary sequences (143). More recently, CEVd infection has been correlated with alteration of rRNAs' maturation and ribosomal stress, potentially connected with viroid symptomatology in tomato (144).

Whether viroids induce epigenetic changes affecting gene expression and pathogenesis is still unknown. Pioneering studies demonstrated that PSTVd infection induces, in a sequence-specific manner, the de novo methylation of a PSTVd complementary DNA transgene in tobacco, thus revealing for the first time the mechanisms of RdDM (145). In the absence of host DNA sequences complementary to vd-sRNAs, the direct involvement of RdDM in viroid pathogenesis is unlikely. However, PSTVd infection induced the expression of genes involved in the RdDM pathway in tomato, thus indirectly promoting hypermethylation of a coinfecting nuclear-replicating single-stranded DNA virus (146). The same mechanism could be involved in the promoter hypermethylation of four host genes observed in potato upon PSTVd inoculation (147). In contrast, demethylation of a ribosomal DNA promoter was reported in cucumber infected by HSVd (148) associated with the impairment of the histone deacetylase 6 activity caused by viroid binding to this protein (149). Altogether these studies suggest that nuclear viroids could interfere with host RdDM in different ways. Whether viroid-induced epigenetic changes are gene dependent or host dependent is still unclear. Possibly, these uncertainties would be clarified by deep methylome analysis.

8. CONCLUDING REMARKS AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

Being exclusively composed of RNA unable to code for proteins, viroids provide a unique model to address structural-functional relationships of noncoding RNAs. They contain all the needed information for an RNA to be capable of using host machineries to replicate, move, and cause diseases in the host plants. This information is compacted in only a few hundred nucleotides, sometimes in overlapping structural motifs. Since their discovery, many functional roles of these noncoding RNAs have been uncovered, with major implications in further understanding RNA biology. Clear examples include the self-cleaving activity mediated by HRzs, the ability to force some host proteins to accept RNA as template/substrate instead of the physiological DNA, and the identification of structural motifs likely involved in RNA trafficking and replication. Viroids are targets and triggers of RNA silencing, and this process has been implicated in pathogenesis, although additional mechanisms also seem to be involved. Further understanding of mechanisms of RNA movement, especially those involved in the chloroplast entry and exit by members of the family *Avsunviroidae*, may reveal novel and relevant RNA signaling networks. Additional fundamental knowledge is finally expected from further characterization of the host factors interacting with viroids. In this respect, viroids could be considered as a magical box, containing valuable information on RNA biology, waiting for further opening and decoding.

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